

Optimal Design of Water Distribution Network Using Parallel Slime Mould Algorithm for Cost Minimization

Glody Malanda Saki ✉

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China;

UNEP- Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development,
1239 Siping Road Shanghai 200092, China

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Abstract

Water distribution networks (WDNs) are vital infrastructures designed to ensure a minimum acceptable supply level to consumers under different operating conditions throughout the design period. Due to their complexity and the substantial investment required for their construction and maintenance, economic aspects have become a primary focus for researchers and engineers. Various evolutionary algorithms (EAs), such as the genetic algorithm (GA), have been utilized to achieve cost minimization while fulfilling hydraulic requirements. This study uses the Parallel Slime Mould Algorithm (PSMA), a variant of the slime mould algorithm (SMA) developed by Wang et al., and implemented to solve the mathematical and hydraulic optimization of WDNs. The PSMA incorporates the Hazen-Williams equation for calculating head loss and pressure constraints to ensure the feasibility of the solution. The proposed method is applied to a benchmark network and compared with results from the GA used by Savic. The PSMA proved effective in optimizing a WDN, achieving a cost reduction of approximately 6.08% compared to the GA while maintaining hydraulic feasibility. However, the pipe sizes showed notable differences, with the PSMA favoring larger diameters for most pipes except pipe 2. These results highlight the potential of PSMA as a powerful tool for WDN optimization, particularly when cost reduction is a priority.

Keywords: *water distribution network, optimal design, genetic algorithm, Slime mould algorithm, pipe optimization.*

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Introduction

Water distribution networks (WDNs) are indispensable infrastructures designed to provide consumers with a minimum acceptable supply level under operating conditions for the whole design period. Today, WDNs are very complex systems requiring a high investment for construction and maintenance (Sacks et al., 1989). An ideal water infrastructure should be

able to provide water demand with the required pressure (Monsef et al., 2019) due to the varying amount of demand during the day. The computational and engineering complexity of WDNs optimal design have been thoroughly investigated over the past years (Farmani et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2015). The design belongs to a group of inherently intractable problems referred to as NP-hard (Quindry et al., 1981). Essentially, NP-hard means that a rigorous

algorithm to find an optimum design using discrete diameters is not a practical possibility. Several researchers have reported algorithms for minimizing the cost through the application of mathematical techniques, such as linear (Sharma & Swamee, 2013; Zangeneh & Mohammad Vali Samani, 2010), non-linear (Eck & Mevissen, 2013) or dynamic programming. It is well known that when diameters are assumed as the decision variables (DV), the constraints are implicit functions of DV, the feasible region is non-convex, and the objective function is multimodal. Hence, conventional optimization approaches result in a local optimum which is dependent on the starting point in the search process.

Over the past years, numerous Evolutionary algorithms (EAs) have been applied to overcome the difficulties posed by deterministic methods. Among these, genetic algorithms (GAs) have been used most extensively (Kang & Lansey, 2012; Krapivka et al., 2009; Zheng et al., 2014a). However, GAs have been primarily applied to relatively simple benchmark problems, such as the 14-pipe problem (Simpson et al., 1994), the New York Tunnels problem with 21 tunnels (Dandy et al., 1996), and the Hanoi problem with 34 pipes (Zheng et al., 2011). In the last few years, there has been a move towards increasing the complexity and realism of the case studies to which GAs are applied, including the rural network with 476 pipes, the BWN-II network with 433 pipes, and the network used by Kang and Lansey (Kang & Lansey, 2012). As a result, computational efficiency has been identified as a key concern for the widespread uptake of GAs for the optimization of large, real-world WDNs.

To address this challenge, two main approaches have been identified in the literature. In the first approach the emphasis was on finding the best possible solution within a realistic computational budget for large and real problems, rather than on attempting to find the global optimal solution, because for such large problems, the global solution is unlikely to be found within a reasonable computational timeframe.

In the second one, efforts have been made to increase the computational efficiency of the

optimization process. This has been done in many ways, including the use of increased computational power, such as parallel and distributed computing (Roshani & Fillion, 2012; Wu & Behandish, 2012), the utilization of surrogate and meta-modeling to speed up the simulation process (Razavi et al., 2012), and the seeding of the initial population of EAs with good solutions obtained using a variety of analytical techniques (Zheng & Zecchin, 2014; Zheng et al., 2014b). Recently, similar concepts have been implemented in conjunction with other optimization techniques (Zhang et al., 2013).

Despite some of the above mentioned methods, many EAs, including GAs, struggle with maintaining an optimal balance between exploration phase which consists of searching new area of the solution space; and exploitation phase consisting of refining existing solutions (Li et al., 2020). They may prematurely converge to suboptimal solutions in multimodal or complex landscapes because their reliance on crossover and mutation operators (Phung & Ha, 2021); require careful tuning of these parameters which can be time-consuming (Mirjalili & Lewis, 2016), and may not always find the global optimum, especially in high-dimensional problems. In the real-world applications, GAs have been widely applied (Li et al., 2020), therefore there is a growing need for algorithms that can handle more complex problems with constraints and dynamic environments. Additionally, GAs may struggle in dynamic or noisy environments where the fitness landscape changes over time (Heidari et al., 2019)

The Slime Mould Algorithm (SMA), inspired by slime moulds' foraging behaviour, inherently balances these two phases due to its unique oscillation mechanism (Li et al., 2020). Its adaptive weight mechanism allows better navigation of such landscapes by dynamically adjusting its behaviour. On the other hand, SMA has fewer parameters and is less sensitive to their settings, making it more user-friendly and robust (Mirjalili & Lewis, 2016), and has shown faster converge, higher accuracy in various benchmark functions and promise in area like engineering design, image processing, and resource allocation, where traditional GAs may fall

short(Li et al., 2024). The SMA was a newly proposed metaheuristic optimization algorithm by Li et al (Li et al., 2020), that took inspiration from the foraging habits of slime moulds. In SMA, the construction of adaptive weights serves to emulate the multifaceted behaviour and morphological shifts of slime mould in response to the constructive and destructive feedback produced by the bio-oscillator. As slime mould approaches a potential food source, its cytoplasmic flow undergoes acceleration. Such an acceleration corresponds to an increase in the thickness of the vein. Consequently, a more rapid formation of the slime mould ensues, leading to a swifter approach towards the potential food source.

The simplified operation code of SMA makes it strong scalability and a significant potential for improvement. Researchers have proposed multiple improvement methods for the defects of the original algorithm, such as succumbing swiftly to confined local minima, low convergence accuracy, and long search time. Improved Slime Mould Algorithm (ISMA) ameliorated with elite and slight modification strategies was introduced by Kaveh et al (Kaveh et al., 2022), the ISMA well performed in structural optimization problems. SMA was hybridized by (Wazery et al., 2021) with opposition-based learning (OBL) to enhance global exploratory capability while mitigating premature convergence. Qiu et al (郑旻 et al., 2023) proposed an improved SMA with Brownian motion and Lévy flight to enhance the exploration ability and interval adaptive opposition-based learning strategy for higher convergence speed. Deng and Liu (Deng & Liu, 2023) introduced a novel search equation that balance explorative and exploitative process, and combined it with centroid opposite-based learning, dynamic random search, and adaptive mutation, substantially improving the limitations of the standard SMA. Wu et al (Wu et al., 2023) proposed a Gaussian barebones mutation and greedy selection enhanced version (GBSMA), which demonstrated superior precision and rapid converge velocity.

Additionally, by reviewing the literature, it seems that slime mould algorithm is widely used. Many

researchers applied the SMA and its variants to engineering optimization problems and others fields. It was applied for solving single and dual-objective economic and emission scheduling (EED) problems taking in account valve point effects (Hassan et al., 2021); determining the best operating rules for complex hydropower multi-reservoir prediction problems (Ahmadianfar et al., 2022); distributed generation (DG) solution of distribution network reconfiguration (DNR) problem (Wang et al., 2022); demand estimation of urban water resource problem(Yu et al., 2021); reliability optimization of micro-milling cutting parameters (Ding et al., 2022), optimal Power Flow Problem (Farhat et al., 2022); A cost-Effective Solution for Non-Convex Economic Load Dispatch Problems in Power Systems (Kamboj et al., 2022) and optimal load-shedding in distribution system problem (Abid et al., 2022) and so on.

Despite its success in other fields, SMA has seen limited application in water resources engineering, and none specifically for the optimal design of water distribution networks. This represents a significant research gap, as SMA's ability to handle complex, high-dimensional problems aligns well with the challenges of WDN optimization. In this study, we propose the use of a **Parallel Slime Mould Algorithm** (PSMA) to minimize the cost of WDNs while meeting hydraulic and operational constraints. PSMA leverages parallel computing to enhance computational efficiency, making it suitable for large-scale, real-world networks. By addressing the limitations of traditional methods and existing EAs, this approach aims to provide a more robust and scalable solution for WDN optimization.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the Slime Mould Algorithm specially the mathematical model. Section 3 outlines the methodology, including problem formulation and the PSMA framework. Section 4 presents the results of applying PSMA to a benchmark network from the literature, followed by a discussion of its performance. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study and suggests directions for future research.

Slime Mould Algorithm

Slime moulds will dynamically choose a better food source according to the quality of the food source, which is equivalent to slime mould seeking the optimal solution. The mathematical model of individual updates in SMA is presented in Eq. (1).

$$X^{t+1} = \begin{cases} X_b^t + v_b \cdot (W \cdot X_A^t - X_B^t), r < p \\ v_c \cdot X^t, r > p \\ \text{rand} \cdot (u_b - l_b) + l_b, \text{rand} < Z \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where X^{t+1} represents the position of slime mold. X_b^t denotes the best value found so far. X_A^t and X_B^t denote two random slime molds, $\text{rand} \in [0, 1]$ and the value range of r is the same as rand . Z is a constant that simulates the living environment, u_b and l_b denote the boundary of the slime mold search space. W denotes the control weight. The range of the parameter v_b is $[-a, a]$, and the range of v_c is $[-1, 1]$, p is a variable selection switch, and its expression is as follows:

$$p = \tanh|S(i) - DF| \quad (2)$$

Where $S(i)$ represents the fitness value of the current slime mould individual, DF represents the global optimal value currently found.

SMA uses W , v_b and v_c to control the movement direction of slime mould. The synergistic effect of W , v_b and v_c , simulates the selective behaviour of slime mould to food, which can make help the slime mold find food better. The values of and are shown in Eqs. (3) – (6).

$$W(\text{index}(i)) = \begin{cases} 1 + r \cdot \log\left(\frac{\text{best } F - S(i)}{\text{best } F - \text{worst } F} + 1\right), \text{require} \\ 1 - r \cdot \log\left(\frac{\text{best } F - S(i)}{\text{best } F - \text{worst } F} + 1\right), \text{others} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{index} = \text{sort}(S) \quad (4)$$

$$v_b = [-a, a] \quad (5)$$

$$a = \text{arctanh}\left(1 - \frac{t}{\text{Max_ite}}\right) \quad (6)$$

Where $S(i)$ is the fitness value of $X(i)$, and require represents the first $S(i)$ half of sorting. $\text{best } F$ and $\text{worst } F$ represent the best value and worst value of fitness currently obtained. index denotes the sorted fitness value sequence.

Because the original slime mould algorithm is easy to fall into the optimal local solutions; therefore, in the algorithm design process, Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2022) introduced a new mechanism based on grouping communication strategy and inertia weight, called the Parallel Slime Mould Algorithm that is presented farther in the following section

Methodology

Problem Formulation

The following mathematical statement of the optimal design problem is presented for a water distribution network (Schaake et al., 1969; Shamir, 1968), which objective is to minimize the total cost of the network, which depends on the pipe diameters and lengths. The primary decision variables are the diameters of the pipes in the network: $D = [D_1, D_2, \dots, D_n]$, D_1 is the diameter of the first pipe, and n is the number of pipes in the network.

$$\text{Total Ccost} = \sum_{i=1}^N \text{Cost}(D_i) \cdot L_i \quad (7)$$

Where $\text{Cost}(D_i)$ is the cost per unit length of the pipe i with D_i and the length L_i , and N is the total number of pipes in the system. To ensure feasibility, a penalty term is added to the objective function if the pressure at any node fails below the minimum requirement:

$$Penalty = \alpha \cdot \sum_{j=1}^m \max(0, MIN_PRESSURE + GROUND_LEVEL_j - PRESSURE_j) \quad (8)$$

Where α is a large penalty coefficient (e.g., 1000), m is the number of nodes, $MIN_PRESSURE$ is the required pressure at node J , $GROUND_LEVEL_j$ is the ground level at node J , $PRESSURE_j$ is the pressure at node J . The total objective function is:

$$Objective = Total\ Cost + Penalty \quad (9)$$

The above function is to be minimized under the following constraints. The Flow into each node must equal the flow out of the node, accounting for the demand at the node:

$$\sum_{i \in in_pipes(j)} Q_i - \sum_{k \in out_pipes(j)} Q_k = DEMAND_j \quad (10)$$

Where Q_i is the flow rate in pipe i , $in_pipes(j)$ and $ut_pipes(j)$ are the test of incoming and outgoing pipes at node j $DEMAND_j$ is the water demand at node j . The pressure at each node must satisfy:

$$PRESSURE_j \geq MIN_PRESSURE + GROUND_LEVEL_j \quad (11)$$

The $PRESSURE_j$ will be calculated using the hydraulic model. The pipe diameters must be selected from a set of commercially available diameters $D_i \in \{D_{available}\}$

For each of the basic loops in the network, the energy conservation constraint can be written as

$$\sum h_f - \sum E_p = 0 \quad (12)$$

Hydraulic Model

To enable them to perform practical pipe flow calculations some function describing the relationship between pressure drop, flow rate, pipe length and pipe diameter is required. Several friction head loss/flow formulae have been developed for that purpose. The most well-known for pressurized pipe systems is the Hazen-Williams (H-W) formula

$$h_f = \frac{10.67 \cdot L \cdot Q^{1.852}}{C^{1.852} \cdot D^{4.871}} \quad (13)$$

Where h_f is the head loss (m), D the pipe diameter (m), and L is the pipe length (m) and Q is the flow rate in m³/s; C is the Hazen-Williams coefficient.

The pressure at each node is calculated by subtracting the head loss from the source head:

$$PRESSURE_j = SOURCE_HEAD - \sum_{i \in path(j)} h_{f,i} \quad (14)$$

Where $SOURCE_HEAD_i$ the fixed head at the source, $path(j)$ is the set of pipes along the path from the source to node j .

The flow rates in the pipes are determined based on the demands at the nodes (Table.1) and the continuity equation. For each node, the flow rates in the incoming and outgoing pipes are adjusted to satisfy the demand

Parallel Slime Mould Algorithm

The optimization problem formulated in the above manner is non-linear due to the energy conservation constraints of Eq. (12). In addition, pipes for water supply are manufactured in a set of discrete-sized diameters thus introducing additional difficulties to the problem of searching for the optimal design. In order to solve this NP-hard problem exactly it is suggested that only explicit enumeration or an implicit enumeration technique such as Dynamic Programming, can guarantee the optimal solution. However, optimal pipe-network design

problems of realistic size become intractable for enumeration techniques. Furthermore, when dealing with processing this issue by original SMA would suffer serious challenges such as: long calculation time, easy losing critical individual in the selection process that cause a severe decline of population diversity, and the search process falling into local optimum, and finally the low dominant individual of local search efficiency cause no achieved convergence.

These are exactly the three strategies applied for the proposed parallelizing approach in this section.

- 1: inertia weight that changes non-linear weight over the iterations.
- Single communication. It means that a randomly selected group is communicated (swap) with the best one.
- Multiple communication that is the best group communicates (swap) with all the other groups.

The inertia weight strategy is implemented as follows. Given SMA's easy loss of key individuals, inertia weight is introduced into SMA. The inertia weight (Wang et al., 2022) changes according to the exponential law, and its expression in Eq. (15)

$$\mu = \mu_{min} \left(\frac{\mu_{max}}{\mu_{min}} \right)^{1 / \left(1 + \frac{10t}{T_m} \right)} \quad (15)$$

Where μ_{max} and μ_{min} are the maximum and minimum value. t is the current iterations, and T_m is the maximum number of iterations.

After introducing the inertia weight coefficient, the update method of Eq. (1) becomes as follows:

$$X^{t+1} = \begin{cases} X_b^t + \mu \cdot v_b \cdot (W \cdot X_A^t - X_B^t), & r < p \\ \mu \cdot v_c \cdot X^t, & r > p \\ rand \cdot (u_b - l_b) + l_b, & rand < Z \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

For the single population problem, this paper uses the communication strategy to enhance SMA. Multi-group communication strategy can improve its performance. The parallel communication strategy is divided the slime mould population into n subgroups, and each subgroup runs SMA independently. After each iteration, the new solution generated by SMA is used to communicate. The communication strategy of subgroups is the key to the PSMA.

The slime mould population N is divided into g groups, and the number of slime moulds in each group is pop ($N/g=pop$). G_{ij} denotes the slime mould in each group, i is the number of groups after sorting ($i \in (1, 2, \dots, g)$) and j is the number of solutions in the groups after sorting ($j \in (1, 2, \dots, pop)$). For example, G_{11} represents the best solution in the first group, and G_{1pop} represents the worst value. Next, take $g = 5$ as an example to explain the two communication strategies.

Strategy 2. For the strategy in Figure 1, the purpose is to realize the communication the optimal particles of the sub-population. G_{11} is the best solution obtained in the first group. With G_{11} as the communication center, one group is randomly selected from the remaining 4 groups, and its optimal solutions is used to communicate with G_{11} , G_{11} will be set to be the same as G_{31} . If G_{31} is worse value of G_{31} 's group. After completing the communication between G_{31} and G_{11} , use the same method to

Figure 1. The communication Strategy 2
Source: Wang et al., 2022

start communication with G_{21} as the communication center, and so on, until each subgroup has completed the communication.

$$G_{r(p-q-1)} = \frac{(X_{best} + G_{b1} \dots + G_{bk})}{(q+1)}, q = 1, 2, \dots, Q \quad (17)$$

Where X_{best} denotes the currently found global optimal solution. r denotes a randomly selected group $r \in (1, 2, \dots, g)$, $r \neq b$. b denotes the current exchange center group, and $b \in (1, 2, \dots, g)$. Q denotes the number of solutions that need to be rounding up.

Strategy 3. Illustrated in Figure 2, the purpose is to realize the communication between the best individual of the global best solution obtained, then the best solution $G_{11}, G_{31}, G_{41}, G_{51}$ of each group is used to compare with G_{21} . If G_{31} can win the global optimal solution G_{21} , it means that the global optimal solution has a greater probability to exist near G_{31} . Therefore, Eq. (17) is used to perturb G_{31} , and if the new solution produced by the perturbation is better than G_{21} , the new solution is used to replace G_{31} .

$$Pos_n = G_{b1} + \frac{E(u_b, l_b)}{F_c} \cdot random(1, dim) \quad (18)$$

Where Pos_n denotes the position of slime mould newly generated after perturbation. G_{b1} denotes the optimal solution currently obtained by the sub-population. E denotes the Euclidean distance of the two vectors. F_c is a constant. Dim denotes the fitness function dimension.

The pseudo code of the proposed algorithm (1) is as follows:

Algorithm 1

Pseudo-code of PSAM

Initialization:

Initialize the search space and dimensions, maximum number of iterations, number of slime moulds (popsize) and randomly divide evenly into G groups, the position of slime mould in each group (X). The fitness function value of each individual was calculated, the best fitness value (f_{best}) and the best function solution (X_{best}) are obtained.

Iteration:

While $t < maxiteration$ do

 for $1: G$ do

 for $i =: (N/G)$ do

 Check whether each solution is within range;

 Calculate the fitness of all slime moulds;

 Update the optimal fitness value (f_{best}) and optimal solution (X_{best}) of the current group

 Use Eq.(3) to calculate W

 end for

 for $i = 1: (N/G)$ do

 Update with the corresponding formula

 Use Eq.(16) to update the position of the slime moulds

 end for

end for

for $i: G$ do

 if rand > 5 then

 Use strategy 2 to communicate

 else

 Use strategy 3 to communicate

 end if

end for

$t = t + 1$

end while

Output: Global optimal solution

Source: (Wang et al., 2022)

Figure 2. The Communication Strategy 3
Source: Wang et al., 2022

An Illustrative Example

Consider the network used by Alperovits and Shamir (Alperovits & Shamir, 1977) shown in Figure 3, which has eight pipes arranged in two loops and is fed by gravity from a constant head is to be at least 20 m above the ground elevation of the node. Table 1 gives basic data. In addition, the minimum diameter (1 inch = 0.0254 m) and the maximum allowed is 24 inches, and also the maximum allowable hydraulic gradient (0.05) constrains were imposed as in the original problem formulation. Table 2a and 2b summarize pipe data.

Table 1. Node Data for the Network Example

Node	Demand (m ³ /h)	Ground level (m)
1(source)	-1120.0	210.0
2	100.0	150.0
3	100.0	160.0
4	120.0	155.0
5	270.0	150.0
6	300.0	165.0
7	200.0	160.0

Source: Savic & Walters, 1997

We further tune some PSMA parameters especially number of groups, for better exploration of the search space, the population size to help avoid premature convergence, inertia weight (w) to balance between exploration and exploitation, and iteration to

give the algorithm more time to converge to a better solution.

Figure 3. A Two-Loop Network

Table 2a. Basic Cost Data for Pipes

Diameter	Unit cost
1	2.0
2	5.0
3	8.0
4	11.0
6	16.0
8	23.0
10	32.0
12	50.0
14	60.0
16	90.0
18	130.0
20	170
22	300.0
24	550.0

Source: Savic & Walters, 1997

Table 2b. Section Data

Section	Length, m	C	Initial flow, m ³ /h
1	1000.0	130.0	1120.0
2	1000.0	130.0	220.0
3	1000.0	130.0	800.0
4	1000.0	130.0	30.0
5	1000.0	130.0	650.0
6	1000.0	130.0	320.0
7	1000.0	130.0	120.0
8	1000.0	130.0	120.0

Source: Alperovits & Shamir, 1977

Incorporating hydraulic gradient constraints into the hydraulic model ensures that the flow velocities in the pipes remain within acceptable limits. The hydraulic gradient S is defined as the head loss per unit length of the pipe:

$$S = \frac{h_f}{L} \quad (19)$$

Where h_f is the head loss in the pipe (m), L the length of the pipe (m). The hydraulic gradient must satisfy the following constraints:

$$0.0005 \leq S \leq 0.05$$

These constraints ensure that the flow velocity is neither too low (which may result in sedimentation) nor too high (which may cause excessive pressure losses or pipe damage). The hydraulic gradient for each pipe is calculated using the Hazen-Williams head loss equation Eq. (12); thus, the hydraulic gradient S is:

$$S = \frac{h_f}{L} = \frac{10.67 \cdot L \cdot Q^{1.852}}{C^{1.852} \cdot D^{4.871}} \quad (20)$$

The objective function now includes penalties for, pressure deficits at nodes; hydraulic gradient violations

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Objective} = & \text{Total Cost} + \\ & \text{Pressure Penalty} + \\ & \text{Hydraulic Gradient Penalty} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The hydraulic gradient penalty is calculated as

$$\text{Hydraulic Gradient Penalty} = \beta \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n [\max(0, 0.0005 - S_i) + \max(0, S_i - 0.05)] \quad (22)$$

Where $\beta = 1000$ is a large penalty coefficient, S_i is the hydraulic gradient for pipe i , n is the number of pipes.

Figure 3. Flow Chart of PSMA Optimization Approach

Results

The analysis based PSMA, using Hazen Williams formula with a friction coefficient of 130 to be consistent with the previous papers (Alperovits & Shamir, 1977; Savic & Walters, 1997; Shamir, 1968).

The PSMA was executed over 5 independent runs, each with the same parameter setting. The optimized pipe diameters and corresponding costs are summarized below in Table. 4. The pressure deficit of 0.0 m indicates that the optimized solution fully satisfies the minimum pressure requirement at all nodes.

Table 3. PSMA parameters

Parameter setting	
<i>Num_group</i>	10
<i>Pop_size</i>	100
<i>Iteration</i>	500
<i>Inertia Weight</i>	[0.2 – 1.0]
<i>lb</i>	1.0
<i>ub</i>	30.0

The convergence plot of the objective function across iterations (Figure 5.) demonstrates that PSMA effectively reduces the cost while maintaining feasibility for hydraulic constraints.

Figure 5. Convergence Curve of Solution Cost Using PSMA

Figure 6. Pressure Distribution at Each Node

PSMA achieved a lower total cost of 393,523.00 USD, compared to the cost achieved by(Eiger et al., 1994) 402,352.00 USD and GANET’s(Savic

& Walters, 1997) 419,000.00 USD. Taking GANET implemented by Savic (Savic & Walters, 1997) as a reference, this represents a cost reduction of approximately 6.08%. The cost reduction is attributed to PSMA’s ability to explore a broader solution space and its parallel communication strategy(Wang et al., 2022) that enhances convergence toward global optima.

Figure 7. Hydraulic Gradient for Each Pipe

Table 4. Optimized Diameter for Two-Loop Network

Num_pipe	Dragan Savic, GA (1997)	PSMA
	D [in]	D[in]
P1	18	28.7
P2	10	9.5
P3	16	15.8
P4	4	27.2
P5	16	24
P6	10	18.3
P7	10	21
P8	1	27.4
Cost (units)	419,000.00	393,523.00
Pressure deficit (m)	0.0	0.0

Note: 1 inch = 0.0254 m

The PSMA produced slightly different pipe diameters compared to GA(Savic & Walters, 1997). For instance, PSMA suggested larger diameter for all pipes except pipe 2, while GA favoured larger diameters for P1, P3 and P5. The differences highlight the trade-offs between pipe costs and hydraulic performance. Which are

influenced by the optimization algorithm's search behaviour.

Both PSMA and GA achieved zero pressure deficits, ensuring that all nodes meet the minimum pressure requirements Figure 6. PSMA's solution maintained hydraulic feasibility while reducing costs, demonstrating its robustness in handling complex constraints.

Finally, PSMA's parallel exploration strategy and adaptive inertia weight mechanism contributed to its superior performance in terms of cost minimization. GA, while effective, may have been limited by its reliance on genetic operators (crossover and mutation), which can sometimes lead to premature convergence or suboptimal solutions.

Discussion

The results demonstrate that PSMA is a competitive alternative to GA for WDN optimization. Its ability to balance exploration and exploitation through parallel group communication and adaptive inertia weights allows it to identify cost-effective solutions without compromising hydraulic performance. The lower cost achieved by PSMA suggests that it is better suited for large-scale optimization problems where cost efficiency is critical.

However, the pipe diameters differ significantly, with PSMA favouring larger diameters for most pipes except P2. The cost reduction suggests that is effective in optimizing the network while maintaining pressure requirements. Besides, the practicality of implementing the larger pipe diameters suggested by PSMA should be evaluated, as larger pipes may have higher installation and maintenance cost, which are not reflected in the cost metric provided.

It should also be noted that the performance of optimization can vary depending on the problem setup, parameter tuning, and computational resources. Further studies could explore the scalability of PSMA for larger networks and compare its performance with other state-of-the-art algorithms.

Conclusion

In this study, PSMA demonstrated its effectiveness in optimizing a water distribution

network, achieving a lower total cost compared to GA while maintaining hydraulic feasibility. The results highlight the potential of PSMA as a powerful tool for WDN optimization, particularly in scenarios where cost minimization is a priority.

Further work could focus on, exploring the scalability of PSMA for larger network, other factors such as resilience and operational constraints, and extending PSMA to handle more complex network and multi-objective optimization problems.

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